

Information (-ei/T) Method and Kaniadakis Entropy

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In (1), we suggested that for both Shannon's entropy (Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution) and Tsallis entropy, the distribution $p(e_i)$ may be obtained from an information method based on $-e_i/T$. In other words, one does not need to maximize \ln of the number of states (or an entropy expression) subject to constraints nor does one require reaction balance. One may begin with a basic focus on information $(-e_i/T)$ and write: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. Next, we argued that in the Shannon and Tsallis cases, one may consider any moment e_i power n $p(e_i)$ (Shannon), or e_i power n $p(e_i)$ power q (Tsallis) and take the derivative $d/dp(e_i)$. We suggested that the first term contains all $-e_i/T$ information and so the second term should be constant, leading to: $p(e_i) d/dp(e_i) F(p(e_i)) = 1$ (Shannon) or $p(e_i)$ power q $dF/dp(e_i)$ (Tsallis) regardless of n . Here 1 has been chosen as a specific constant.

In this note, we try to apply this approach to Kaniadakis entropy. In the Kaniadakis scheme, the starting point is again the basic $(-e_i/T)$ one, namely, one considers an $\ln_k(\exp(-e_i/T)) = -e_i/T$. Although the exact approach of setting the second derivative term to a constant does not produce \ln_k , we suggest that the information approach still holds if one argues that even though the first derivative contains all of the $-e_i/T$ information, there is no reason why the second term cannot contain this same information. In that case one obtains \ln_k (Kaniadakis) (such that $k \rightarrow 0$ yields \ln , whereas with the Tsallis case, it is $q=1$).

Information (-ei/T) Method for Finding a Distribution

In (1) (Parts 2 and 3), we argued that one may find the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions without maximizing the \ln (number of states) or an explicit entropy expression subject to constraints. We further argued that by changing the constraint, i.e. the moment of e_i used, one obtains a different result. In addition, we suggested that neither does one need to use reaction balance. Instead, we argued for a general procedure which holds for any moment: $\sum_i e_i$ power n $p(e_i)$ (Shannon) or $\sum_i e_i$ power n $p(e_i)$ power q (Tsallis).

The basic recipe was to begin with an information $(-e_i/T)$ focus:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Here } p(e_i) \text{ is an unnormalized probability.}$$

The second step is to mimic an e_i power n moment via:

$$p(e_i) \{F(p(e_i))\} \text{ power } n \quad (\text{Shannon}) \quad \text{or} \quad p(e_i) \text{ power } q \{F(p(e_i))\} \text{ power } n \quad (\text{Tsallis}) \quad ((2))$$

We argued that when taking $d/dp(e_i)$, the first term $(d/p(e_i))$ acting on $p(e_i)$ displays all of the $-e_i/T$ information, so the second term may be considered to be constant. In other words, it has no further $-e_i/T$ information to reveal. For any n , this leads to:

$$p(e_i) dF/d p(e_i) = 1 \quad (\text{Shannon}) \quad \text{or} \quad p(e_i) \text{ power } q dF/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad (\text{Tsallis}) \quad ((3))$$

This allows one to solve for $F(p(e_i))$ and hence $p(e_i)$. In the Tsallis case, there is the extra constraint that $q=1$ should yield $F(p) = \ln(p)$, i.e. the Shannon result.

If one tries to apply this recipe to the Kaniadakis case, it does not work. Nevertheless, we argue that the Kaniadakis result does follow from a slightly generalized consideration. In particular, instead of forcing the second term of the derivative $d/dp(e_i)$ to be a constant because the first term displays all of the $(-e_i/T)$ information, one may argue for the second term revealing the same $-e_i/T$ information as the first. This then yields the Kaniadakis entropy such that for a parameter $k=0$, one has $F(p) = \ln(p)$ again. Thus, we suggest that the Kaniadakis scheme is consistent with the $-e_i/T$ information method, with this modification.

Kaniadakis Scenario

The Kaniadakis scheme begins with the same $-e_i/T$ informational focus on $-e_i/T$, namely the insistence on (2):

$$\ln_k(p_k(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((4))$$

It also defines entropy as $S_k = - \sum_i p(e_i) \ln_k p(e_i)$ such that $k=0$ yields $\ln_k = \ln$ ((5)) (2).

As a result, it appears that $p(e_i)$ is used to calculate moment e_i power n . We write:

$$p(e_i) \{ F(p(e_i)) \}^{\text{power } n} \text{ and take } d/dp(e_i) \quad ((6))$$

The first term, with $d/dp(e_i)$ acting on $p(e_i)$, yields $\{ F(p(e_i)) \}^{\text{power } n}$ which displays all of the $-e_i/T$ information for the n th moment.

One may argue, however, that the second term may yield the same information, i.e.

$$p(e_i)^n \{ F(p(e_i)) \}^{\text{power } (n-1)} dF/dp \text{ goes as } (-e_i/T)^{\text{power } n} \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{This implies that: } p(e_i) dF/dp = (-e_i/T) \text{ constant} \quad ((8))$$

((8)) suggests that $F(p)$ be written as a power of p because $F(p) = -e_i/T$. A simple scheme is to introduce a single parameter k ($0 < k < 1$) and consider both:

$$p^{\text{power } k} \text{ and } p^{\text{power } -k} \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{Then: } \{ p^{\text{power } k} - p^{\text{power } -k} \} / (2k) \quad ((10))$$

satisfies ((8))

Thus, the Kaniadakis $\ln_k(x)$ function ((10)) may be obtained from a modified $-e_i/T$ information approach.

We note that $\ln k(p(e_i))$ yields (2):

$p(e_i) = \{ \sqrt{1+kx} + kx \}^{-1/k}$ ((11)) (One may substitute ((11)) into ((10)) to immediately see this)

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) we suggested a method for finding a statistical distribution without maximizing $\ln(\text{number of states})$ or entropy subject to constraints or using reaction balance for Shannon's and Tsallis cases. The basic idea was to write: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and focus on $-e_i/T$ information. Using the form of e_i power n moments, one may write: $p(e_i) \{F(p(e_i))\}^n$ (Shannon) or $p(e_i)^q \{F(p(e_i))\}^n$ (Tsallis). Taking $d/dp(e_i)$, we argued that the first term displays all of the $-e_i/T$ information so the second term may be a constant. In the Tsallis case, for $q=1$, one should also obtain the Shannon result $F = \ln$.

This approach does not work for the Kaniadakis scheme of $-p(e_i) \ln k(p(e_i))$, but we suggest that a modified one does. If the first term of the derivative reveals all of the $(-e_i/T)$ information, then the second term may also reveal the same information instead of being a constant. It simply does not reveal any new information. Using this approach, for any e_i power n moment, one may write: $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = \text{constant } (-e_i/T)$ and obtain a simple $1/(2k) \{ p(e_i)^k - p(e_i)^{-k} \}$ result. Thus, we suggest that the Kaniadakis scheme is in keeping with the $(-e_i/T)$ information approach of finding distributions.

References

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